

Project acronym: ASSESS DHT

Grant Agreement Number: 101137347

Project full title: Development and harmonisation of methodologies
for assessing digital health technologies in Europe

Website: www.assess-dht.eu

D1.4 Data Management Plan

Version: 1.0

Status: Final

Dissemination Level: Public

Submission Date: 17.07.2024

Work Package: WP3 Data Management, Protection and Cybersecurity

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Funded by the
European Union

Revision History

Version	Date	Changes made	Author(s)
0.1	14.05.2024	Draft structure	Nathan Lea (I-HD)
0.2	24.05.2024	Chapters 2.1 and 2.2 drafts	Nathan Lea (I-HD)
0.3	14.06.2024	Chapters 2.3-2.6 drafts	Nathan Lea (I-HD)
0.4	12.07.2024	Final draft sent for peer review	Nathan Lea (I-HD) Dipak Kalra (I-HD)
0.5	15.07.2024	Peer review	Farah Diehl-Fahim (EMPIRICA)
0.6	16.07.2024	Finalisation following peer review	Nathan Lea (I-HD) Dipak Kalra (I-HD)
1.0	17.07.2024	Submission to EC	Farah Diehl-Fahim (EMPIRICA)

Abstract

The report provides the data management plan for ASSESS DHT. The project will be handling data that relates to standards, legislation, best practice and guidelines. The project will not handle any data relating to individuals for its research purposes. Personal data will only be handled on behalf of consortium members and their associates or affiliates for the purposes of managing the project. The report uses the European Commission template for Data Management Plans and has included an additional review for sustainability. The plans will be updated as the project proceeds and updates will be provided as a later deliverable.

Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of HaDEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable 1.4 provides the data management plan for ASSESS DHT. The project will be handling data that relates to standards, legislation, best practice and guidelines. The project will not handle any data relating to individuals for its research purposes. Personal data will only be handled on behalf of consortium members and their associates or affiliates for the purposes of managing the project.

This deliverable uses the European Commission template for Data Management Plans and has included an additional review for sustainability.

The plans will be updated as the project proceeds and updates will be provided as a later deliverable.

1 Introduction

This deliverable is based on the Data Management Plan template provided by the European Commission for Horizon 2020 projects¹.

ASSESSDHT as a project will not be processing any personal data for research purposes, rather it will review technical and standards specifications along with an assessment of the appropriate regulations. Other than contact details processing for Project related business (including potentially usernames and password management) and authorship details, there is no other personal data processing foreseen. The DMP has therefore been drafted with this in mind.

¹ Full template available here for reference: https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/gm/reporting/h2020-tpl-oa-data-mgt-plan_en.docx

2 Data Management Plan Assessment

2.1 Data summary

Aspect	Response/explanation
<i>Purpose of the data collection/ generation and its relation to the objectives of the project</i>	<p>Data collected will relate to standards specifications, development libraries, assessment criteria and process management only. There will be little personal data involved in the project, with the exception of authorship details, routine consortium communications and management needs and reporting back to the funders.</p> <p>The overall aim of the project is to develop gold standard assessment processes, criteria and alignment across regulatory approvals for existing, new and forthcoming regulations, including but not limited to: GDPR, AI Act, EHDS, Medical Device Regulation, Clinical Trials Regulation, Data Governance Act and the associated assessments that exist, are in development and need alignment (including Health Technology Assessments).</p> <p>The goal is to align and produce a comprehensive series of regulatory compliance guidance tools, quality assessment criteria and enhance existing quality assurance certifications with a comprehensive view of the new regulations.</p>
<i>Types and formats of data generated or collected by the project</i>	<p>Data will be related to standards specifications, metadata cataloguing, data quality metrics and associated specifications, interoperability standards and spec, regulatory compliance specifications and processes, assessment criteria and proposed quality labelling for data quality and governance of personal health data use.</p> <p>Administrative data for names, organisations, contact details and roles will be held for consortium management only.</p> <p>The data sources will likely be in documents and spreadsheets.</p>
<i>Any re-use existing data and how this will be done</i>	Purely information held in existing standards and documents
<i>The origin of such data</i>	Standards bodies, research institutes, industrial and regulatory authority details for standards and compliance.
<i>Expected size of the data</i>	Uncertain
<i>Likely users of the data</i>	Consortium partners conducting research and assessments of the standards, specifications and regulatory processes.

2.2 FAIR data- Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Aspect	Response/explanation
<i>Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable, identifiable and locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism</i>	Not as standard. Many of the specifications are shareable at a high level of abstraction, but require in some cases licences for use (e.g. ISO and IDHIS). Any additional materials produced by the project may only be available under licence.
<i>What standard identification mechanism used (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers)</i>	In most cases and any produced materials will use DOIs
<i>Is meta-data available through catalogue?</i>	It would be likely where the catalogue may include data quality assessment metrics, safety and regulatory compliance requirements and data models.
<i>Can meta-data be used for search?</i>	This will be considered as the project progresses.
<i>Naming conventions used</i>	This is yet to be determined.
<i>Clear versioning supported?</i>	This is yet to be determined.
<i>Additional keyword search supported?</i>	This is yet to be determined.
<i>What metadata will be created using which standards?</i>	This needs to be assessed as the materials are reviewed and developed.

2.2.1 Making data openly accessible

Aspect	Response/explanation
<i>Will data be made openly available as the default?</i>	Unlikely – some registration and licencing may be expected from the project partners at the completion of the Project
<i>Which datasets will NOT be openly available and why?</i>	As above
<i>How will the data & meta-data be made accessible (e.g. by deposition in stated repository)?</i>	A repository (or repositories) will be considered for the materials developed by the project
<i>If known repository, what arrangements explored?</i>	Not yet known
<i>If project-specific access, then:</i>	[If known describe otherwise this detail to be filled in Phase 3]

Aspect	Response/explanation
<i>Data Access Committee</i>	This is unlikely as the materials are non personal in nature. An access committee may be excessive oversight if appropriate terms can be agreed by the Consortium
<i>Any conditions for access (i.e. a machine-readable licence)</i>	Likely licensing using modern distribution
<i>What methods or software tools will be needed to access the data?</i>	N/A
<i>Documentation for software</i>	N/A – no software is expected to be developed.
<i>Availability of software</i>	As above
<i>Institution and researcher vetting process/procedures - describe</i>	These will not be required (except in the case of licencing where the Project will decide if any materials can be shared with individuals or those with association with appropriate organisations.

2.2.2 Making data interoperable

Aspect	Response/explanation
<i>Are the data produced in the project interoperable</i>	N/A
<i>If not, explain why not</i>	The data will be specifications that will guide the development of interoperable software and data handling
<i>Data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies used</i>	The standard corpus will be referred to (ICD, SNOMED etc.).
<i>Standard vocabularies used</i>	This is yet to be determined.
<i>Mappings from uncommon or project-specific ontologies or vocabularies to more commonly used ontologies</i>	This will be supported and required by the specifications as established in Interoperability and data management standards.

2.2.3 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

Aspect	Response/explanation
<i>Will data be available for onward data-sharing/re-use?</i>	No – it is likely that the Project will maintain licence terms for all users of the specifications and onward sharing will not be permitted.
<i>Approach to data licensing for onward use</i>	N/A – these are standards that will guide onward use of research data and will support development of other DMPs for specific projects.

Aspect	Response/explanation
<i>Likely date for data availability for onward use</i>	N/A
<i>Explain any restriction on date of availability</i>	N/A
<i>Possible restrictions on onward data-sharing</i>	As specified above – the project will produce specifications and guidance on inward data sharing use only.
<i>Data retention policy (including availability for data-sharing)</i>	Ongoing specifications support for versioning only – no retention.
<i>Description of data quality assurance processes</i>	As specified in the data quality components.

2.3 Allocation of resources

Aspect	Response/explanation
<i>Estimated project costs for making data FAIR</i>	N/A
<i>Data management responsibility across the project</i>	The European Institute for Innovation through Health Data (I-HD).
<i>Resources required for long term preservation (costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)</i>	To be determined.

2.4 Data security

Aspect	Response/explanation
<i>Data security measures used (including data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)</i>	TBD as part of a DPIA process and Platform Development work. It will focus on: Any Central hosting platform security and data access; User Access credentials for the Interfaces (likely MFA)
<i>Where data will safely be stored (in certified repositories for long-term preservation and curation). Provide details.</i>	TBD as part of a Data Protection Impact Assessment process (if run – this is unlikely given the minimal personal data use) and / or Platform Development work for the project.

2.5 Ethical aspects

Aspect	Response/explanation
<i>Any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing</i>	Mainly the balance between upholding IPR and allowing open access to a wider community.
<i>References to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA) – if relevant</i>	N/A
<i>Questionnaires dealing with personal data</i>	None planned
<i>How is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation sought in such questionnaires?</i>	This is not applicable as no personal data is being used for research purposes.

2.6 Sustainability and Future Compliance Risk Management

Aspect	Response/explanation
<i>What elements are planned for sustainability activities moving forward?</i>	The sustainability plans are being developed and will evolve as the project proceeds. Sustainability may involve a curated standards and guidance library platform. This will be addressed in WP1. IPR will need to be honoured within the terms of the Consortium Agreement.
<i>What certifications would be required for a sustainability plan to go to market? (e.g. MDR, AI Certifications)</i>	This project is a basis for recommending and specifying what certifications would be required so is unlikely to be certified those standards given that the results will not involve processing of personal data (where e.g. ISO 27000 series certifications would arguably be excessive). ISO 9000 for any spun put entity may be appropriate, or for existing partners who may retain responsibility for the ongoing curation of any standards libraries that are produced.
<i>What data retention and best practice documentation is required to achieve this? Specifically, how can we ensure the quality, assessment of bias, traceability of results and recommendations, transparency, repeatability etc.</i>	These are minimal and would require only the versioning of different libraries of materials that are produced.
<i>What risk management is envisaged to support sustainability? E.g. DPIA Updates, Ethical Review, Tool management, Legacy System reliance etc.</i>	TBD
<i>Is there a data flow diagram available?</i>	N/A